

PROBLEMS OF OFFENSES AND DEVIANT BEHAVIOR OF ADOLESCENTS AND WAYS OF USING THE EDUCATIONAL AND UPBRINGING OPPORTUNITIES OF THE MEDIA IN THEIR MORAL EDUCATION

Sh.Taylakova

PhD, Associate Professor at Journalism and Mass Communications University of Uzbekistan (JMCUU)

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Abstract. *This article, using the educational capabilities of the media, highlights the issues of spiritual and moral education of schoolchildren prone to crime and delinquency among adolescents.*

Keywords: *information, communication, globalization, education, media, minors, deviant behavior.*

Introduction. Today, the rapid development of information and communication technologies has led to the fact that human life is enveloped in a non-stop flow of information, and the creation of a global information system in the world. This, in turn, became the basis for the formation of a global information society. The difficult fact is that globalization has an unprecedented impact on all aspects of human life and society. In this case, the growth of unlimited information flows, the likelihood that the news of an event from one side of the world will instantly reach this side and affect social reality will increase, which will lead to a reanalysis of the entire society and state institutions. State security through the prism of globalization poses a need. Currently, a large percentage of socio-political and ideological information, which is spreading very quickly through the media, is of concern in different countries of the world.

Powers seeking to take over the world are trying to use information as a weapon. In other words, on the one hand, information becomes important as a resource that serves to expand the spiritual world of mankind, enriching human knowledge and thinking, and on the other hand, information separates a person from his personality, nation, homeland, and eventually turns him into a complete degenerate. It's no secret to anyone today that it is becoming a weapon. Even now, many countries are forced to take special measures to protect their culture, traditions and spiritual values from the influence of foreign information. For this reason, it is extremely important to understand the content of incoming information, correctly interpret it and draw conclusions. At the same time, when the process of globalization is proceeding at a rapid pace, the most important task of any mass media is to win its place in the global information space and achieve progress. At the same time, when the development of Uzbekistan is steadily moving along the path of building a legal democratic state and civil society, it is necessary to increase the efficiency of this important process, form public opinion in ensuring socio-political stability and democratic renewal, and help the population to actively participate in the reform process. An important role played by the media. The most important task of the mass media is to objectively cover the domestic and foreign policy of our country, based on the diversity of opinions and views on the events taking place around us, and the goals of further emancipation of our society.

Today it is no secret to anyone that the media are becoming both an information field and a socio-political, spiritual and educational department. Our national media in these processes carry out their activities on the basis of priority tasks determined on the basis of the social, economic, political, legal, environmental, cultural life of society. Below we will focus only on parts of the tasks of TV channels related to educational processes.

Television programs, whether they be shows, films or videos, have a strong influence on a person's worldview. The impressionability of television products causes the birth of negative or positive thoughts and ideas in the minds of minors. Therefore, a representative of the sphere of television production should consider the sphere of television journalism primarily as a tool aimed at the development of social culture and spirituality.

The second medi-pedagogical feature of TV shows is characterized by the fact that the event takes place right before the eyes of the TV viewer. In addition to impression, this feature gives a dramatic spirit to the hearts of minors, the medium disappears between the event and the student, and the person becomes face to face with the world.

If a mistake is made in the press, on television and radio, the whole country will know in an instant. Today's television and radio channels are broadcast worldwide via satellite. In this process, the whole world can become aware of the flaws in the broadcast. Therefore, it is important that every media product prepared on our national television and radio channels has educational features and corresponds to our national mentality. The process of forming a national information space in our country also depends on this. Compared to press and radio journalism, a TV journalist should have at least ten professions and industry knowledge. On television, sometimes educational features of the image are shown on the screens without any commentary.

Main results and discussions. In the course of the study, the organizational and pedagogical functions of television programs that serve to improve the spirituality of minors have been clarified: preventive, cognitive, integrative, reflective, socio-pedagogical, cultural and recreational needs.

Preventive function - the preventive function of television programs serves to form in the personality of minors the qualities of caution and sensitivity to be sensitive and aware of various dubious media materials, to take the right actions when confronted with them.

The integrative function is to inform adolescents about the reforms being carried out in our country, to form a sense of ownership in them, to combine their interests with the interests of the country (integration).

Reflexive function - serves as a means of self-education of the student through the analysis of his spiritual, cultural, scientific worldview, his duties and responsibilities to the Motherland and people through the content of television programs.

The informative function of television programs serves to inform minors about the news happening in the world and in our country, to provide them with scientific, artistic, spiritual knowledge, and to develop an information culture.

Socio-pedagogical - the social-pedagogical function of television shows serves to form moral qualities, moral education, adaptation to life and development of social skills in minors.

Cultural-recreational - the cultural-recreational function of television shows serves to provide cultural entertainment through the showing of programs and to realize the creative abilities of minors and to develop their aesthetic needs.

Taking into account the importance of mass media in human education and development, we came to the conclusion that programs for the audience of minors should be prepared based on the cooperation of journalists and pedagogues. Then, educational properties of media products prepared under the direct cooperation of mass media and educational institutions will be further improved.

Taking into account the importance of the media in the upbringing and development of a person, we came to the conclusion that programs for a minor audience should be prepared on the basis of cooperation between journalists and educators. Then the educational properties of media products prepared with the direct cooperation of the media and educational institutions will be further improved.

“Television does not give anything to a child. Readers need to get the most out of each show. To do this, the child needs to see useful things. Don't let the TV deprive your child of books, lessons and rest. To do this, the parent should talk with the child about the movie they watched and interesting, intelligent programs, cartoons [3].

When a teenager tells his parents, grandparents, teacher or friends about the programs he saw on television, during this period the media-pedagogical features of television programs begin to influence the child. During the discussion, the experience of watching the program doubles. However, if you look at the question from the other side, then recently the number of small viewers who do not move in front of the TV has been enormously increasing.

“Some parents think that if my child watches TV, he will be away from idleness and the bad influence of the street. As a result, watching TV becomes a natural need for the child, he leaves other important things and runs to the screen. As a result, parents will say, “If you don't do your homework, you won't watch TV... Watching too much TV will damage the child's eyes and nerves.” Minors can also lose their knowledge as a result of watching too much TV. Media products broadcast on television should be used as a learning tool. To do this, there are pedagogical tips on the need to mark weekly TV shows with a felt-tip pen at the beginning of the week. In conclusion, it is worth saying that the parents themselves are an example for the child by what they watch in front of the TV. Forbidding a child who watches clips and films suitable for adults will not give a good result. Maybe what conclusions did the child draw from the TV shows, clips and films he watched, and how did these programs influence him? It is possible to effectively and correctly use the educational functions of media products by getting answers to these questions from the child, correcting the child's opinion if necessary and directing it to education.

In the global information environment, the media should pay more attention to increasing the quantity and quality of analytical and critical programming aimed at youth audiences. This attitude requires journalists to take a more responsible approach to their work. After all, when a journalist prepares material on the topic of students, he is responsible for “what does the student feel?”, “What does the student read, what does he see?”. This is a great responsibility” [4]. At the same time, it will be possible to draw public attention to the solution of the problems raised in these materials. Studying the process of using the educational opportunities of the mass media in the education of minors, we were once again convinced that the sphere of influence of television, i.e. visibility, among other media in the life of student youth is quite wide [5]. The convincing impact of television information is enhanced by various technical and artistically spectacular means and techniques (montage, genre, musical and noise scenery). Audio and video with

increased coverage is sure to attract the attention of minors. (Visuality is also expressed in accessing the Internet through mobile phones and watching shows, clips and films).

The Russian psychologist L. Trubitsina writes in the article “Media and Psychological Trauma”: “Sometimes traumas have a bad effect, especially on children and adolescents. After children have witnessed terrorist attacks or bombings, preschool children often develop psychiatric disorders such as panic attacks and sleep disturbances. Interestingly, children of this age are better at distinguishing such everyday life events from the depiction of events in feature films. There were many complaints from teachers about the increased propensity of adolescents to act aggressively after the psychological trauma caused by the terrorist attacks in Moscow [10].

Taking into account that TV shows, radio programs and Internet messages occupy an important place in the spiritual worldview of minors, teachers of educational institutions in this process mainly focus on the following:

determine changes in the state of mind, state of mind and mental state of minors caused by the media;

determination of measures to combat negative situations that arise in the minds and hearts of adolescents;

to explain the essence of ensuring the prevention of information threats among minors through the products of the national media, that is, to form critical views in their minds in relation to information;

the formation of adolescents' skills and abilities to deal with information threats through the products of national media;

determine the adolescent's awareness of everyday events in the classroom using various innovative methods and provide objective information;

the use of television programs and videos promoting heroism, patriotism, hard work in educational processes to awaken in minors a sense of self-confidence and the development of critical thinking;

effective use of media materials in the education of minors' volitional qualities;

it is necessary to pay attention to the formation of a culture of information consumption among minors in relation to information disseminated through some foreign media.

Conclusion. Today, both the family and the school do not take enough into account the possibility that the information spread through the mass media can change the situation in different directions in ideological processes. In educational institutions, it is still shown that mass media are viewed only as a tool that helps to diversify the educational process and obtain additional information. Unfortunately, in some cases, neither pedagogues nor parents can consider mass media materials as a unique, important socio-pedagogical factor. Failure to recognize this in the ideological education of the growing young generation in the daily pedagogical process should be recognized as a serious pedagogical deficiency.

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